

ENHANCING STUDENTS' COGNITIVE PERFORMANCE IN A GUIDED INQUIRY-BASED APPROACH IN GRADE 7 SCIENCE

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ABSTRACT

Guided inquiry-based approach, a student-centered learning environment encourages students to actively engage in the learning process and develop critical thinking skills by providing them with guiding questions and opportunities for investigation. In this context, the study examined the students' cognitive performance in a guided inquiry-based approach in Grade 7 science of Miaray National High School in the School Year 2024-2025, where thirty-seven (37) students participated in the guided inquiry-based approach and thirty-five (35) in the nonguided inquiry-based approach. A quasi-experimental research design was used. Two research instruments were used, such as academic and non-academic assessments. A teacher-made test with Cronbach alpha of 0.88 was used to measure cognitive performance. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, mean, percentages, and standard deviation were used to examine the students' level of cognitive performance, and an Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to compare significant differences between groups. The findings of the study revealed that the students' cognitive performance when exposed to guided inquiry-based approach increased and performed better than the nonguided inquiry-based approach. However, both groups were found below 74% mark, which indicates they "*Did Not Meet Expectations*". Further, the analysis of covariance indicated a highly significant difference in cognitive performance with an F-value between the two groups is 34.28 with a probability value of 0.000 ($P < 0.05$). With these findings, teachers are recommended to employ guided inquiry-based approaches to enhance the students' cognitive performance.

Keywords: *cognitive performance, guided inquiry-based approach*

INTRODUCTION

Science educators have a great opportunity to enhance students' cognitive performance in science. Cognitive performance is characterized as the learner's capacity to carry out different cognitive tasks like memory, attention, problem-solving, and decision-making. Cognitive concepts relate to the different cognitive processes and abilities that support student's intellectual growth and academic success (Roeser & Eccles, 2015).

However, the recent Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) results in 2022, as highlighted by Acido and Caballes (2024), revealed the unsatisfactory performance of the Philippines in science, ranking 77th out of eighty-one countries globally. Most Filipino students performed below average in the science literacy test and creative thinking skills, as did most international students (Coryton, 2023). The current National Achievement Test (NAT) results in the Division of Bukidnon showed a 31.55% score in science, which is very low compared to the passing rate of 75% (DepEd Bukidnon, NAT 2024). In the context of Miaray National High School, there were one hundred seventeen enrolled students in Grade 7 for the academic year 2024-2025. Of these, 62 or 53% were considered poor in their science performance, 33 or 28% gained a grade of 80-84 or satisfactory level and 29 or 25% are in 75-79 fairly satisfactory level in science, based on the 1st Quarter Curriculum Management Support System (CMSS) (Miaray National High School-CMSS,2024-2025).

Furthermore, this performance of students ought the science teachers to improve their instructional practices by implementing student-centered approaches that is anchored on scientific inquiry. One of the teaching approaches that has gained increasing attention in recent years is the guided inquiry-based approach, a student-centered learning environment which encourages students to actively engage in the learning process and develop critical thinking skills by providing them with guiding questions and opportunities for investigation (Banchi & Bell, 2008; Bruder & Prescott, 2014). According to Nasution (2018), the guided inquiry-based approach is one of the models that emphasizes science skills, thinking ability, and scientific research. The guided inquiry-based approach has the potential to significantly improve students' cognitive performance in science education.

Thus, researchers conducted this study to investigate the potential of a guided inquiry-based approach to enhance the cognitive performance of grade 7 science students.

Research Questions

This study examined the students' cognitive performance in a guided inquiry-based approach in Grade 7 science of Miaray National High School, Miaray, Danggagan, Bukidnon.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of the students' cognitive performance when exposed to guided inquiry-based approach and those exposed to nonguided inquiry-based approach in terms of;
 - a. Pretest; and
 - b. Posttest?
 2. Is there a significant difference on the students' cognitive performance when exposed to guided inquiry-based and those exposed to nonguided inquiry-based approach in terms of;
 - a. Pretest; and
 - b. Posttest?
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METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a quasi-experimental research design to examine the effects of guided inquiry-based approach on students' cognitive performance. The participants of the study were the two intact sections of Grade 7 at Miray National High School, Miray, Dangcagan, Bukidnon of S.Y.: 2024-2025. The Grade 7 level were chosen as participants of the study because 62 or 53% are poor in their science performance based on the 1st quarter Curriculum Management Support System (CMSS). One section was exposed under guided inquiry-based approach which consists of thirty-seven (37) students while the other class was under a nonguided inquiry-based approach which consists of thirty-five (35). A pretest and posttest were administered to determine the significant difference in students' cognitive performance when exposed to guided inquiry-based approach and nonguided inquiry-based approach.

The research instrument used in this study is a research-made cognitive test. The researcher constructed 80 multiple-choice tests, which covered the following topics namely: System models, earthquakes and the Sun's influence on Earth as reflected in the Grade 7 Lesson Exemplar which is aligned to MATATAG Science Curriculum. All the items were formulated using Structure of Observed Learning Outcomes (SOLO) Framework. The questionnaire has been validated by three experts in Earth Science and revised by the experts. After content validation, it was then field tested to Grade 8 students to measure its reliability. Out of 80 multiple-choice tests, 45 items were found statistically reliable with a Cronbach alpha of 0.88 which is a reliable measure.

The quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency, mean, percentages, and standard deviation examining the students' level of cognitive performance in science. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to examine any significant differences in students' cognitive performance in science concerning their pretest, posttest, and retention after being exposed to guided inquiry-based approach and those exposed to non-guided inquiry-based approach.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Level of Students' cognitive performance as exposed to Guided Inquiry-Based Approach and Nonguided Inquiry-Based Approach.

Raw score	PRETEST				POSTTEST				Qualitative Interpretation
	GIBA		NGIBA		GIBA		NGIBA		
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
41-45	0	0	0	0	9	24.32	0	0	Outstanding
39-40	0	0	0	0	4	10.81	0	0	Very Satisfactory
36-38	0	0	0	0	2	5.41	3	8.57	Satisfactory
34-35	0	0	0	0	1	2.70	4	11.43	Fairly Satisfactory
33-Below	37	100	35	100	21	56.76	28	80	Did not meet the expectations
Total	37	100	35	100	37	100	35	100	
MPS	46.18		42.79		74.23		58.16		
QI	DNME				DNME		DNME		

Before the intervention, the guided inquiry-based approach group achieved a MPS of 46.18 while the nonguided inquiry-based approach group obtained 42.79, which interpreted as "Did not meet the expectations" (DNME). These results might be attributed to the students' prior knowledge or misconceptions on the specific contents thus they failed to comprehend the topic lessons on Earth and Space concepts. It also illustrates that the key concepts presented were noted new and seemed unfamiliar to the students.

The findings implies that both groups require elaborations for better conceptual understanding hence it needs improvement. Furthermore, the similarity in the MPS values suggests that both groups possess a comparable level of knowledge, as the numerical disparity between them is minimal.

This finding presents the same results with the study of Bansale (2023) that pretest results are generally concentrated at the lowest cognitive performance which supports that concepts are still new and unfamiliar to the students. Guskey and Mctinghe (2016) showed that pretest is given at the beginning of every lesson which leads to a failing scores of students. As stated by Balansag (2021) students find it difficult to obtain good or better results in pretest because concepts haven't been known during their early grade level. Similarly, Sombilon (2023) reported that students needed more prior knowledge and experience about the lesson because their conceptual understanding is relatively poor to comprehend the given lesson.

The posttest results revealed that the students obtained a noteworthy increase in the MPS of 74.23 “Did not meet expectation”. The breakdown of these posttest results is as follows: nine (9) or (24.32%) achieved an outstanding level, four (4) or (10.81%) attained a very satisfactory level, two (2) or (5.41%) reached a satisfactory level, one (1) or (2.70 %) achieved a fairly satisfactory level, and twenty-one (21) or (56.76) did not meet the expected performance level. On the other hand, the data also revealed an increase in the overall cognitive performance of students in the non-guided inquiry-based approach via nonclasspoint instructional tool, with the following distribution: Zero (0) or (0%) achieved an outstanding level, zero (0) or (0%) reached a very satisfactory level, three (0) or (8.57%) attained a satisfactory level, four (4) or (11.43%) achieved a fairly satisfactory level, and twenty-eight (28) or (80%) did not meet the expected cognitive performance level. These guided inquiry-based approach and non-guided inquiry-based approach both achieved a “Did Not Meet Expectation” Level in the Overall Mean Percentage Score.

These findings obtained similar results with the research of Kaçar et al. (2019), on the effects of inquiry-based learning on student’s cognitive performance across various grade level and publication types. They found out that with guided inquiry-based approach it enhances students’ cognitive performance. Similarly, the study of Ertikanto et al. (2015) and Malik et al. (2015), showed differences on the students’ ability to think at high-level of cognition when compared between inquiry-based and conventional learning. Also, the study of Zheng et al. (2018) on the effectiveness of combined technology tools such as mobile devices using inquiry-based learning as an instructional approach had a positive effect on student’s cognitive performance. Thus, these findings collectively reinforce the effectiveness of guided inquiry-based approach in enhancing students’ cognitive performance.

Table 2. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the Students’ Cognitive Performance in the Posttest

Group	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
Guided Inquiry-Based Approach	37	74.23	16.00
Nonguided Inquiry-Based Approach	35	58.16	16.16
TOTAL	72	66.42	17.90

Source	SS	dF	MS	F-Value	Sig.
Corrected Model	329930.223 ^a	3	109976.741	725.979	.000
PRETEST (Covariate)	7650.999	1	7650.999	50.506	.000
GROUP	10388.448	2	5194.224	34.288	.000
Error	10452.637	69	151.487		
Total	340382.860	72			

Legend: *Significant at P<0.05*

Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the students' cognitive performance in the posttest with the pretest as the covariate between groups. The mean percentage scores of the Guided Inquiry-Based Approach group is 74.23 (SD=16.00) and the Nonguided Inquiry-Based Approach group had a mean score of 58.16 (SD=16.16). As reflected the group exposed to Guided Inquiry-Based Approach obtained high mean scores as compared to Nonguided Inquiry-Based Approach. This implies that the students under the Guided Inquiry-Based Approach performed better than the Nonguided Inquiry-Based Approach in terms of their cognitive performance. The F-value between the two groups is 34.28 with a probability value of 0.000 ($P < 0.05$) indicating a highly significant difference. A significant difference existed between two groups in relation to cognitive performance.

These findings suggest that educators could implement guided inquiry-based approach, particularly utilizing instructional tools like classpoint, to enhance students' cognitive performance. The significant differences in performance underscore the need for more interactive and engaging teaching strategies to foster better learning outcomes. As observed students under a guided inquiry-based approach group are more engaged in the science class as they are exposed to an inquiry instruction and they construct ideas easily as they collaborate among themselves. They become more confident and exhibited understanding of concepts while performing the learning activities. These experiences contributed an increased on their cognitive performance for they are with guided inquiry-based approach.

This current study conforms with the study of Aulia et al. (2024) and Ural (2016) who reported a significant increase on students' academic attitudes and performance through guided inquiry-based approach. The study of Basijan (2024) shows similar findings with the current study through interactive games via Classpoint instructional tool in teaching mathematics it enriches conceptual understanding on the subjects. The same result with the study of Caballes and Morata (2024) on the use of digital game-based learning with Classpoint and had improved the student's numeracy skills as compared to the traditional teaching method. Furthermore, the results contradict to the study of Husnaini and Chen (2019) as the study found no significant difference between the performance outcomes of students taught using a guided inquiry-based approach and those taught using the demonstration method (a more traditional approach) in some contexts, indicating that guided inquiry in physical laboratory did not always outperform traditional demonstration methods.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn:

1. The implementation of guided inquiry-based approach in relation to students' cognitive performance showed an increase in their posttest as compared to the students under nonguided inquiry-based approach. Thus, exposure to guided inquiry-based approach indicates a positive impact on students' cognitive performance.

2. A significant difference existed between groups in relation to cognitive performance as exposed to guided inquiry-based approach. The mean difference was in favor of the guided inquiry-based approach group. Hence, exposure to guided inquiry-based approach successfully enhanced students' cognitive performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are hereby given:

1. Educators may apply the guided inquiry-based approach in other disciplines to investigate how it enhances cognitive performance, including improvements in content knowledge, learning processes, and learning outcomes within those subjects.
 2. Future researchers may consider other scientific skills such as indicator or components. Other alternative modes of scientific skills may be compared to other subjects to see their preference and relevance.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher observed ethical conduct throughout the study. An IERC clearance was secured from Central Mindanao University regarding the ethical considerations of the study. Then, researcher also secured permission from the teachers and students. Collected information remained anonymous and was stored securely. Any potential conflicts of interest between the researchers and participants were addressed and disclosed.

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